

The role of wildlife in driving ecotourism and visitor satisfaction on the Osa Peninsula of Costa Rica:
The Lapa Rios case

QUESTIONARY ON ARRIVAL

Nationality:

Gender:

Age:

Highest education:

Occupation:

Was wildlife one of your motivations to visit Lapa Rios Ecolodge? Choose the most appropriate.

- Yes
- No

How important was wildlife vs other motivations? Please rank them in order of preference from 1 (the most important) to 10 (the least important).

RANK HERE

- Installations and Location
- All-inclusive service (i.e. accommodation, meals, tours, transfers)
- Lapa Rios Private Reserve
- Wildlife sightings
- Guided Tours
- Excellent and Personalised Customer Service
- Quality-Price ratio
- Visitors Reviews/Word to Mouth
- Travel Agency Package
- Sustainability

What wildlife do you prefer to see during their visit? Please select five, using the list with animal pictures as a guideline, and rank them in order of preference from 1 (the most preferred) to 5 (the least preferred).

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.

How likely, in your opinion, are you to see any of the species selected above while visiting Lapa Rios Ecolodge? Tick the most appropriate for each specie

Specie	Extremely likely	Somewhat likely	Neither likely nor unlikely	Somewhat unlikely	Extremely unlikely
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					

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List of species and groups provided to LR guests

QUESTIONARY BEFORE DEPARTURE

Were you satisfied with the wildlife sights during their visit? Choose the most appropriate.

- Extremely Satisfied
- Somewhat Satisfied
- Neither Satisfied or Dissatisfied
- Somewhat Dissatisfied.
- Extremely Dissatisfied

¿What were the most satisfying wildlife sights? Please, state 3 of your most preferred.

- 1
- 2
- 3

Did the Lapa Rios experience/tours increase your knowledge of the Osa Peninsula wildlife? Choose the most appropriate.

- Yes, a great deal
- Yes, a moderate amount
- Yes, a little
- No, it did not